

Interaction of Montmorillonite Clay and Trace Element Cations

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The release of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} by H^+ ions has been studied by (i) interacting the corresponding saturated clays with varying concentrations of H_2SO_4 solution and (ii) allowing varying amounts of a synthetic cation-exchanger in its H-form (called H-resin) to equilibrate with the clays through a suitable membrane. The H-resins are kept in cellophane bags and immersed in the suspensions of the clay salts. The H-resin/clay salt systems are designed to simulate to a certain extent the exchange process at the plant-root environment. The results of these experiments are presented in the form of exchange isotherms. The order of release of the metal ions is: $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} = \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+}$ for the H_2SO_4 and/or H-resin systems, but the H_2SO_4 isotherms are placed somewhat higher than the corresponding H-resin isotherms. In the case of Cu^{2+} , the difference between the two systems is more marked than in the others.

Plants take up their mineral nutrients from the soil by a process of ion exchange. The plant tissues contain acid groups, capable of binding and exchanging cations, and basic groups with a similar role towards anions. In the process of exchange between the plant and the soil, the clay fraction of the latter plays the most important part. Hence a study of the exchange behaviour of the clay fraction reveals, generally, the exchange characteristics of the soil as a whole.

The exchange studies are generally carried out in colloidal suspensions which hardly simulate the soil-plant root environment. The application of synthetic ion-exchangers and natural ion-adsorbing materials, such as the clay minerals and clays, as substitutes for soils in plant nutrition experiments has meant real progress by the elimination of certain variables and by a better knowledge of the composition and physico-chemical properties of the root environment. The results of such investigations have recently been reviewed by Wiklander¹. On account of the rather acid properties and the electronegative character of the root-surface membrane, the young plant roots behave essentially as acidoids²⁻⁵, exhibiting pronounced cation exchange and possessing exchange capacity similar to, often greater than, the clay colloids⁶⁻¹³. From their studies on air-dried, finely ground

1. Calman and Krossman, "Ion Exchangers in Organic and Biochemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N.Y., 1957, Chapter 31, p. 573.
2. Lundegårdh, *Kgl. Lantbruks-Högskol. Åvsn.*, 1940, **3**, 233.
3. MacGillivray and Tensdel, *Proc. Koninkl. Ned. Akad. Wetens., Ser. B*, 1954, **57**, 513.
4. Tensdel *et al.*, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1944, **63**, 97.
5. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1946, **65**, 539.
6. Brown, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1955, **18**, 296.
7. Elgabsly and Wiklander, *Soil Sci.*, 1949, **67**, 419.
8. Gray *et al.*, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1953, **17**, 235.
9. Mattson, *Kgl. Lantbruks-Högskol. Åvsn.*, 1948, **15**, 306.
10. Mattson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, **16**, 457.
11. Schuffelen and Loojjes, *Proc. Ned. Akad. Wetens.*, 1942, **45**, 844.
12. Williams and Coleman, *Plant & Soil*, 1950, **2**, 243.
13. Jain, *C. r. Sci.*, 1950, **28**, 71.

alfalfa and on ordinary bath sponge, respectively, McGeorge¹⁴ and Mattson¹⁵ have established that plant non-root tissues also possess cation-exchange properties.

For simulating a soil-plant root environment, Brown and Albrecht¹⁶ took H-clay as the exchanging material and separated this from the clay salts by a collodion membrane. Synthetic resin exchangers being less complicated and often much more versatile than the clays, Chatterjee¹⁷ made use of them to simulate plant roots or similar exchanging materials in his studies on the concentrated suspensions of clays. Later on Wiklander and Stahlberg¹ (unpublished data) used this technique in their study of the influence of Ca²⁺ on the exchangeability and availability to plants of K⁺, Na⁺, Cu²⁺, and Mn²⁺ adsorbed on kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite clays. The amounts of H-resin used in their experiments were large enough to make possible an uptake of all the cations released from the clay without decrease of the rate of exchange. They also used oxidised pea-roots in place of H-resin. In both the cases they could relate the rate of release with the degree of Ca²⁺ saturation.

In the present investigation on the exchange studies of the clay salts of the trace elements with H-resin, the technique of Brown and Albrecht¹⁶, as modified by Chatterjee¹⁷, has been utilised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of H-resin.—Amberlite—IR 120 (Na-form of a sulphonated polystyrene resin) was used in this investigation as the cation-exchange resin. According to Welch *et al.*¹⁸, the availability of cations is much higher on such a nuclear sulphonic acid resin, in comparison to that from other resins. The H-form was produced by leaching it with 0.1N-HCl till the leachate composition became constant. It was washed till free of the chloride ion and then dried.

The base-exchange capacity of the H-resin was determined by a method (*vide infra*) similar to Ganguly's¹⁹ KCl-KOH method for H-clay. To an accurately weighed H-resin (0.5 g.) were added a saturated solution of KCl (20 ml) and water (20 ml) and the mixture was shaken mechanically for 6 hr. The contents were filtered and the acid liberated was determined by titrating the filtrate with 0.1N-KOH. The b.e.o. was found to be 480 m.e./100g.

Exchange Study.—A known amount of the H-resin was taken inside a small cellophane bag, fastened to one end of a Pyrex tube and moistened with water. The tube was fitted into a cork and immersed in the suspension of the clay-salts contained in a conical flask. The cork, which fitted into the mouth of the flask, supported the tube with the cellophane bag. The other end of the tube was sealed by a small piece of cork for preventing evaporation. The system was allowed to remain in this condition with occasional shaking till equilibrium was attained.

14. *Plant Physiol.*, 1932, 7, 119.

15. *Ibid.*, 1942, 10, 58.

16. *Missouri Agr. Expt. Sta. Res. Bull.*, 1951, No. 477, 1.

17. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2, 111.

18. *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1954, 18, 127.

19. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1417.

Preliminary experiments with the Ni-clay showed that the equilibrium was attained in about 3 weeks, but the arrangement was not dislodged before 5 to 7 weeks. The time required to attain equilibrium is thus much longer in these system than are usually observed in exchange reactions¹⁷.

The amount of the cation exchanged for hydrogen ion of the H-resin was then determined by leaching the resin with $N-H_2SO_4$ solution (4 or 5 instalments, shaking each time for 2 hr.) and analysing the leachate for the cation by methods reported earlier²⁰⁻²¹.

In earlier experiments, the clay salts after equilibrium were also analysed for exchangeable cation by acid-leaching. The results were found to agree with determinations made from acid-leaching of the resin.

The amounts of H-resin had been varied in such a manner that the total amounts of H^+ ions associated with it corresponded to 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 3.0 times the symmetry concentration.

The replacement of any cation from clays being dependent on the degree of saturation, experiments were carried out for comparative purposes with only the base-saturated clays.

The amounts of cation exchanged with varying symmetry concentrations of the H^+ ions are recorded in Tables I and II and in Fig. 1 to 5.

TABLE I

*Amount of resin/acid.	% M^{2+} exchanged with H-resin.	Exch. ratio: H_2SO_4 .	Exch. ratio: H-resin/ H_2SO_4 .	*Amount of resin/acid.	% M^{2+} exch. with H-resin.	Exch. ratio: H_2SO_4 .	Exch. ratio: H-resin/ H_2SO_4 .
A. Cu-clay: Exchangeable Cu^{2+} = 63.0 m.e./100 g. Cu-clay taken = 0.3024 g. Total volume = 42 ml.				B. Mn-clay: Exchangeable Mn^{2+} = 59.0 m.e./100g. Mn-clay taken = 0.134 g. Total volume = 20 ml.			
0.5	17.7	23.5	0.753	0.5	26.4	25.0	1.058
1.0	25.3	34.0	0.744	1.0	38.9	38.0	1.000
1.5	32.9	45.3	0.726	1.5	48.6	48.6	1.000
2.0	32.9	59.2	0.618	2.0	50.0	52.8	0.947
3.0	44.7	65.6	0.661	3.0	51.4	61.1	0.841
C. Ni-clay: Exchangeable Ni^{2+} = 67.0/100g. Ni-clay taken = 0.146 g. Total volume = 20 ml.				D. Co-clay: Exchangeable Co^{2+} = 68.0 m.e./100g. Co-clay taken = 0.143 g. Total volume = 20 ml.			
0.5	21.0	22.7	0.926	0.5	22.4	22.0	1.018
1.0	29.7	34.0	0.851	1.0	20.4	31.6	0.930
1.5	34.1	39.8	0.851	1.5	35.0	38.4	0.888
2.0	39.2	47.1	0.832	2.0	43.6	42.4	1.028
3.0	46.2	52.0	0.886	3.0	45.9	51.4	0.914

*In terms of symmetry concs.

N.B.—M stands for different cations.

For comparison, the results of exchange reactions between the clay salts and H_2SO_4 , as measured by the usual procedure, viz., by direct addition of H_2SO_4 to the clay salts, are also shown in the same table.

20. Basu, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1958, 6, 71.

21. Basu and Mukherjee, *ibid.*, 1965, communicated.

TABLE II

Amount of resin (S)	..	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0
% Zn ²⁺ exchanged with H-resin	..	30.6	30.4	50.3	50.1	67.8

DISCUSSION

The exchange isotherms (cf. Figs. 1 to 5) have the usual features and enable us to draw the following conclusions:

(i) The sequence of release of metal ions from their clay salts by H⁺ of the H-resin is: Zn²⁺ > Mn²⁺ > Ni²⁺ = Co²⁺ > Cu²⁺.

FIG. 1 Exchange isotherms of clay-salts against H-resin.]

FIG. 4. Exchange isotherms of Ni-clay against H-resin and H₂SO₄.

(ii) The isotherms of the clay salt- H_2SO_4 systems studied are generally above the corresponding isotherms of the clay.salt+H-resin systems.

FIG. 5. Exchange isotherms of Co-clay against H-resin and H_2SO_4 .

(iii) The ratios of percentages of exchange with H-resin and H_2SO_4 vary from 0.62 to 0.75 for Cu-clay, 0.84 to 1.06 for Mn-clay, 0.83 to 0.93 for Ni-clay, and 0.89 to 1.03 for Co-clay. This also follows from (ii) above.

These results would mean that even H^+ ions bound to the resin are quite effective in releasing exchangeable Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , etc. ions although not as much as free H^+ ions.

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